

SURFACE TREATMENT OF CARBON FIBERS BY ULTRAVIOLET LIGHT+OZONE: ITS EFFECT ON FIBER SURFACE AREA AND TOPOGRAPHY

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1 Ultraviolet Light Surface Treatment

Carbon fibers require surface treatment in order to establish suitable adhesion to polymeric matrices. In general, the surface treatments are oxidative processes and can be carried out in either liquid phase or gas phase. Three major methods are currently practiced by carbon fiber manufactures: 1. anodic oxidation, a wet process where solution concentration and amperage must be maintained; 2. exposure to ozone gas at elevated temperature; and 3. treatment in caustic solutions such as nitric acid. Surface treatments result in improved fiber-matrix shear properties through a two part mechanism. First, a weak, defect-laden outer layer is removed from the surface of the fiber which generates a stronger surface to sustain shear loading. The second contribution of surface treatments is the deposition of chemical functionalities, most notably oxygen containing moieties that improve wetting and bonding between the fiber and matrix [1].

This work describes the use of ultraviolet (UV) light in the presence of ozone (UVO) as a method for treating graphitic surfaces, a technique which has been successfully applied for the surface treatment of many polymer materials (2-5). UVO treatment involves several complimentary processes to potentially oxidize a surface. First, photons with wavelengths of less than 300 nm have sufficient energy to break many chemical bonds forming radicals on the surface which are then available to react with oxygen (see Table 1). Second, UV photons with wavelengths of 254 nm have sufficient energy to disassociate ozone into atomic oxygen, a highly reactive species, which can oxidize the surface. Additionally, UV photons with

wavelengths of 185 nm can disassociate oxygen to form atomic oxygen which is a very reactive species capable of oxidizing many materials.

The use of ultraviolet (UV) light in the presence of ozone (UVO) has been investigated as a method for treating carbon fibers [6,7]. In our previous work, data was presented on carbon fibers that were treated on a batch basis [8-11]. Tows were wound on a quart frame placed in a chamber that was flushed with 700 ppm ozone while irradiated with a 300 watt pulsed xenon UV spiral lamp for various periods. This batch processing yielded small amounts of treated tows, typically 1 -2 linear feet.

Since then a continuous UVO treatment line has been assembled that provides much greater amounts of fiber that allow for enhanced characterization such as BET and tow weight loss analysis. A comprehensive array of tests have been conducted to characterize fiber surface properties, tensile strength, interfacial adhesion, and unidirectional composite properties.

2 Materials and Experimental

Carbon fibers from 2 different precursors were obtained from their manufacturer in their "as received" state without any surface treatment. AU4 (Hexcel Corporation, Stamford, CT) is derived from polyacrylonitrile (PAN), with a tensile modulus of 228 GPa. For comparative purposes, values for AS4 are included, the analog to AU4 that has been given an anodic oxidative surface treatment by the manufacturer. The other fiber evaluated in this study was derived from coal tar pitch (PITCH), Dialead K63712 (Mitsubishi Plastics Inc., Tokyo, Japan), and has a modulus of 634 GPa. The Dialead

has a wagon wheel structure of graphitic ribbons in a radial array shown in Fig 1.

The continuous UVO treatment system at MSU consists of two 30 inch xenon flash lamps connected in series. A fiber unwinder-rewinder handling system passes the tow through the treatment chamber with minimal tension. The fibers are maintained at a distance of 2 cm from the flash lamps. UVO exposure time is controlled by changing the line speed. The production yield of this pilot scale system for 12k tow treated for 90s is approximately 100-150 grams per hour, depending on the fiber density.

An advantage of using pulsed lamps is their emission of high peak energy light pulses of short duration. Compared to continuous xenon lamps, pulsed xenon lamps have substantially greater emission in the 150-250 nm range, shown in Fig 2. The higher energy output of the pulsed lamps is capable of breaking many chemical bonds outlined in Table 1. The energetic ultraviolet light can directly interact with the fiber surface to disrupt and change chemical bonds creating favorable conditions to react with the gaseous oxygen radicals. The result of the UVO process is the rapid oxygenation of the carbon fiber surface and an increase in surface energy which is beneficial to fiber wetting by the matrix and enhanced fiber-matrix bonding.

To evaluate the effect of UVO treatments on fiber mechanical properties, tensile strength measurements were conducted on single filaments following UVO treatment. The test method was in general compliance with ASTM D3379, now retired. Samples were tested on an electromechanical screw drive unit fitted with a 500 gram load cell (United Testing Systems Inc., Huntington Beach, CA). A fiber gage length of two inches was tested at 0.05 inches per minute to failure. A minimum of 20 filaments were tested to determine the mean tensile strength of "as received" and UVO treated fibers.

Changes in surface chemistry as a function of UVO treatments were evaluated using x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). XPS measurements were performed using a 5400 ESCA work station (Physical Electronics Inc., Chanhassen, MN). X-Ray photons were generated from a polychromatic Mg anode (1254 eV). The analyzer was operated in the

fixed energy mode employing a pass energy of 89.45 eV for survey scans and 17.9 eV for utility scans.

Carbon fiber surface area as a function of UVO treatment time was measured by the BET method using krypton gas as the adsorbate. Measurements were collected on a Micromeritics 2020 physisorption analyzer (Micromeritics Instrument Corporation, Norcross, GA). Prior to BET analysis the samples were vacuum degassed at 100 °C for ~4 hours and cooled to room temperature. Approximately 1 gram of carbon fiber was measured on two individual samples to obtain an average value of the surface area as a function of UVO treatment time.

Raman spectroscopy was used to characterize changes in the near-surface graphitic order generated by the UVO treatment. A LabRAM ARAMIS (Horiba Scientific, Edison, NJ) confocal Raman microscope was used to acquire the spectra utilizing a 532.15 nm Nd-YAG laser as the source illumination. The incident beam was focused through a 50x objective to produce a spot size on the apex of a fiber approximately 2 μm in diameter. The backscattered Raman signal was resolved using an 1800 gr/mm diffraction grating and collected in 5 second exposures; 25 exposures were averaged to produce a spectrum. Three fibers per treatment condition were scanned. Subsequent data analysis was performed using LabSpec 5 (Horiba Scientific) and consisted of a polynomial baseline correction followed by Lorentzian peak fit and area integration.

The effect of UVO treatment on interfacial adhesion was evaluated with the single fiber fragmentation test. This test provides a sensitive means to quantify the interfacial shear strength of continuous fibers in a polymeric matrix. For this research, a simple DGEBA epoxy cured at stoichiometry with meta-phenylene diamine was used as the polymeric matrix. A schedule of 2 h at 75 °C followed by 2 h at 125 °C was used to process the single fiber fragmentation coupons. The embedded fiber diameters were measured using an optical microscope fitted with a video caliper. Details for conducting this test can be found elsewhere [1]. Seven to 10 fragmentation coupons of each fiber type were averaged to calculate a mean value of the interfacial shear strength.

UVO treated fibers from the continuous treatment line were impregnated with epoxy resin on a drum winder to fabricate unidirectional prepreg. The resin was the same as used for the fragmentation test, Epon 828 with 1,3meta-phenylene diamine. The prepreps were consolidated to 12 ply unidirectional composites processed by standard autoclave techniques at 100 psi using the same thermal cure schedule employed to make the fragmentation coupons. Two fiber-matrix adhesion dominated tests were conducted on the composites, namely 3-point shear and 90°-flexural strength.

The findings presented here are the most comprehensive collection of data on UVO treated carbon fibers. The effect of UVO treatments on fibers surface chemistry and structure, fiber tensile strength, interfacial adhesion and ultimately, composite performance, are presented.

3.0 Results

Previous Work

Previously, the effect of UVO treatments on PAN-based AU4 carbon fiber were explored by the MSU team using a 300W pulsed spiral flash lamp (6-11). In one set of experiments the treatment chamber was flushed with 700 ppm ozone during the UV irradiation, and treatments times ranged from 5 seconds to 10 minutes.

The surface of the untreated “as received” AU4 fibers possessed an O/C of 0.02. Following just 5 seconds of exposure to a UVO treatment this ratio increased to 0.12 (Fig 3), a tremendous level of oxygen uptake in a brief time. The fibers continued to oxidize with UVO treatment times of up to 90s where a plateau was reached with an O/C atomic ratio of 0.22. Following a UVO treatment of 10 minutes, the O/C atomic ratio increased to 0.27. The observed levels of surface oxidation go well beyond what is expected for a graphitic surface, where only the edge groups are considered vulnerable to oxidative attack.

The AU4 fibers were also treated for the same time periods using UV only without supplemental ozone gas. After 60 seconds, the O/C ratio increased to 0.05 for the UV treated AU4 fiber, well below the

same fiber treated for just 5 seconds when supplemental ozone is used.

Similarly, AU4 fibers treated at room temperature with 700 ppm ozone without UV light resulted in substantially lower amounts of surface oxidation than fibers treated to a combination of ozone and UV. After 60s exposure the ozone treated fiber O/C ratio was 0.06, similar to the fiber subjected to only UV irradiation for the same time. The combination of energetic ultraviolet light in the presence of small amounts of supplemental ozone produced the most rapid uptake of surface oxygen.

In our previous studies using the 300W spiral lamp, we documented that there is no loss in carbon fiber tensile strength for UVO treatment time of 60 seconds. Although the scatter in tensile strength is characteristically large for these fibers, the results confirm that under the UVO condition employed in our previous studies the fiber tensile strength was not adversely affected and may have benefited from treatment.

Following UVO treatment we previously reported an increase in the fiber surface roughness measured using atomic force and scanning tunneling microscopy. Surface roughness increased with longer UVO treatment times. These results show that the UVO treatment is affecting the graphitic surface of the fiber, perhaps by erosion of the outermost graphitic layers.

Our previous research documented the increase in interfacial shear strength for fibers that were UVO treated. Using the single fiber fragmentation test, the interfacial shear strengths of the PAN and Pitch fibers with the epoxy matrix exhibited significant improvement following UVO treatment, see Fig 4. The interfacial shear strength of AU4+UV-Ozone was more than twice the baseline AU4 system. Furthermore, the interfacial shear strength of the AU4+UVO system was greater than the value attained for the commercially treated AS4 system. As expected the IFSS for the high modulus as received Pitch fiber, 5.67 MPa, is much lower relative to the PAN fibers. However, after UVO treatment, the IFSS increased nearly 400% to 27.89 MPa, surpassing the commercially treated PAN AS4 fiber.

Current Work

The development and implementation of the MSU continuous fiber treatment line allows large amounts of UVO-treated fiber to be generated. This provides the opportunity to investigate properties that could not be evaluated on the small amounts of product produced by the UVO batch process. Properties of fibers treated on the continuous UVO line are investigated and compared to previously reported data collected on fibers treated in the batch chamber.

Surface Chemistry

The AU4 fiber following 90s of UVO treatment on the dual lamp continuous fiber treatment line increased surface oxidation from 2 atomic percent to 14.2 atomic percent, which corresponds at O/C ratio of 0.021 to 0.179. This is lower than the level of oxidation found for AU4 treated in the batch mode using the 300W lamp system, see Fig 5. For batch treatment, fibers tows were manually spread on a frame, ensuring that all fibers in the tow receive exposure to the UV radiation. In the new continuous treatment line the tow is not dispersed to the same degree, and it is likely that there is shadowing of interior fibers preventing the same level of UV exposure. As a consequence there is lower average surface oxidation of the tow.

The pitch Dialead K63712 exhibited an increase in surface oxygen concentration from 2.6% in the as received condition to 5.7% after 90 s of UVO treatment, a 120% increase. The highly graphitic pitch fibers continue to exhibit an increase in surface oxidation for UVO treatment times of 180s. The highly ordered pitch fibers will have fewer lattice edges compared to the AU4 fibers, resulting in less opportunity for oxidation of the fiber surface by the UVO treatment.

Surface Morphology

Raman spectroscopy was used to evaluate the surface structure of the UVO treated Dialead fiber. The in-plane stretching vibrations of the sp²-carbon in a graphene layer generate a Raman band centered at 1580 cm⁻¹. A perfectly ordered graphite crystal will exhibit only this band (the G band) in the first order region of 1100-1800 cm⁻¹. As defects and disorder in a graphitic material increase, new bands will appear at 1350, 1500 and 1620 cm⁻¹. The band at 1350 cm⁻¹ is termed the D band in recognition of

its appearance as defects increase in graphitic materials [12]. The integrated intensities of the G and D bands can be used to calculate a disorder ratio in the form of $A_{1350}/(A_{1350}+A_{1580})$. The first-order Raman spectra of the untreated and UVO treated Dialead K63712 fibers displayed well-defined D and G peaks nominally located at 1350 cm⁻¹ and 1580 cm⁻¹, respectively. The disorder ratio of the fibers increased monotonically with treatment time [Fig. 6] and reached a plateau at 90s UVO treatment. These results show that the UVO treatment is disrupting the fiber surface.

The BET surface area measured by krypton adsorption increased nearly 50% for the AU4 fiber following UVO treatment, from 0.42 m²/g for the as received fiber to 0.62 m²/g after 90s of treatment, see Fig. 7. In comparison, the Dialead K63712 surface area increased 20% following 90s UVO treatment and 35% following 180s. The more rapid increase in surface area of the AU4 fibers is due to the greater number of edge sites available for reaction than the highly ordered pitch fiber.

Also measured was the mass of 8 foot length sections of K63712 fiber following UVO treatment. As shown in Fig 8, the fibers exhibited a weight loss following UVO treatment. Based on an average fiber diameter of 11 μm, the estimated rate of diameter reduction is approximately 20 nm per minute using the UVO treatment settings utilized in this study. Fig 8 shows the fiber diameters measured on the single fiber tensile specimens. A simple regression analysis gives a diameter reduction rate of ~150 nm per minute of UVO treatment, an order of magnitude greater than the reduction predicted by mass loss. One plausible explanation is that the fibers harvested for tensile testing typically come from the outside of the bundle. Fibers that are positioned in the bundle interior are not readily removed in sufficient lengths for testing. It is likely that the outer fibers receive more UVO treatment and have a faster rate of erosion than interior fibers.

Fiber Tensile Strength

Single fiber tensile strengths of UVO treated K63712 are reported in Figure 9. The scatter is large which is characteristic of high modulus carbon fibers. The lowest tensile strength was measured for the 90s UVO treated fiber, 2.08 GPa. The T-test

comparing the As Recd to the 90s UVO at the 0.05 probability level supports the null hypothesis that the two sets of data are from the same population; there is no statistical difference in tensile strength and the UVO treatment has not affected the tensile strength.

Interfacial Shear Strength and Composite Properties

Following 45s UVO treatment the interfacial shear strength of K63712 doubled from 12.2 to 27.4 MPa (Fig 10). Longer treatment times did not result in higher values of IFSS. The IFSS for the K63712 treated on the continuous fiber system are marginally lower than the fibers treated in the batch system reported in our previous studies.

Unidirectional composite panels were made using AU4 fiber UVO-treated for 90s. For comparison, unidirectional composite panels were made with AS4, the commercially available surface treated analog of AU4. The interlaminar shear strength increased from 47.5MPa to 82.3MPa following UVO treatment of the AU4 fiber, Fig 11. The ILSS of AU4-UVO fiber was equal to the commercially treated AS4. Similar findings were found for the 90⁰-flexural strength, a test that is dependent on fiber-matrix adhesion. Following treatment, the flexural strength increased from 21.4 MPa to 55.4 MPa, a value that is marginally greater than the AS4 fiber measured at 50.2 MPa, see Fig 12. The ILSS and 90⁰-flexural strength show that the UVO treatment is effective at promoting composite properties.

Cost Analysis

Based on information received from surface equipment manufacturers, comparative cost models were developed for 5 surface treatment systems: Plasma treatment; Corona Treatment; Solvent Wash; Flame Treatment; and UV Treatment. The costs associated with each method of treatment were normalized to treat a square inch of the surface. Only the cost of operating the equipment for a unit of time was considered and the amount of surface area treated in this unit time calculated. The analysis was extended to a production line treating a five square foot surface area of polymer per part at a rate of 200 parts per hour.

A process comparison and cost analysis of the UV process indicates that it is at least equal to current technologies in effectiveness of cleaning and pretreating surface for painting and adhesive bonding.

Summary.

The continuous UVO fiber treatment line was successfully employed to treat carbon fiber in larger quantities than the batch process enabling a comprehensive study to be conducted that detailed the changes in fiber surface chemistry and structure, interfacial properties, as well as critical composite properties. The UVO process caused the rapid oxygenation of the fiber surface in both PAN and Pitch based fibers. Following UVO treatment, the fiber surface area increased, which is complementary to the increase in fiber surface roughness previously reported. Both the fiber mass per length of tow and fiber diameter were reduced following treatment, confirming that the UVO process is removing material from the fiber surface. The single fiber fragmentation test found greater levels of interfacial adhesion for UVO treated fibers, which translated to increases in composite interlaminar shear strength and 90⁰ flexural strength. UVO treatment is an effective, fast, inexpensive and environmentally friendly method for the treatment of PAN and Pitch fibers.

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Fig 1 SEM micrograph of Dialead K63712 showing radial alignment of graphitic structure.

Fig. 2 Spectral emission of xenon lamps.

Fig. 3 AU4 Surface oxygen concentration as a function of UVO treatment time.

Table 1. UV spectral and chemical bond energies.

Wavelength nm	Energy kJ/mol	Bond	Bond Energy kJ/mol
365	328	C-C	348
254	472	C=C	607
185	647	C-H	413
		O-O	138
		O=O	490
		O-H	462

Fig. 4 Interfacial shear strength of UVO treated fibers.

Figure 5 UVO-treated AU4 fiber. Filled diamonds from batch UVO chamber; large open diamond from continuous treatment line.

Fig. 6 K63712 pitch fiber disorder ratio as a function of UVO treatment time.

Fig. 8. K63712 pitch fiber mass loss and diameter reduction following UVO treatment.

Fig. 7 Surface area of AU4 (PAN) and K63712 (Pitch) following UVO treatment.

Fig. 9 Single fiber tensile strength of K63712 (pitch) UVO-treated fiber.

Fig. 10 Interfacial shear strength of K63712 (Pitch) UVO-treated fiber in epoxy matrix.

Fig. 11 Epoxy –Carbon Fiber Composite interlaminar shear strength.

Fig. 12 Epoxy- Carbon Fiber Composite 90° flex strength.